

“INDUSAC communication strategy and materials”

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SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students and 300 researchers by project end. The INDUSAC counts with a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that counts with the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this document D4.1 “INDUSAC communication strategy and materials” is to present an effective communication strategy to disseminate the project objectives and results to the European community through the use of appropriate communication materials, media channels and events oriented towards the target group. Detailed actions are explained in the document.

The document “INDUSAC communication strategy and materials” is prepared at an early stage of the project (in month three) and addresses the following issues:

- What are the objectives of the dissemination effort?
- Who is particularly affected by the INDUSAC project?
- Who would be interested to know about the outcomes?
- What is the most effective way to reach relevant stakeholders for INDUSAC?
- How to measure the efficiency of the awareness-raising and dissemination plan?

This document is the first deliverable of Work Package 4 – Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication. It is conceived as a “working” strategy, so where necessary, presented plans will be regularly updated and properly improved during the implementation of the project.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

BAX	Bax&Company, member of the INDUSAC consortium
BIC	Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley, member of the INDUSAC consortium
CCIPB	Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Pécs-Baranya, member of the INDUSAC consortium
CIT UPC	UPC Technology Center, member of the INDUSAC consortium
CLC	Co-location Centre
CUT	Cyprus University of Technology, member of the INDUSAC consortium
EIT	EIT Manufacturing CLC East, member of the INDUSAC consortium
EU	European Union
IAC	Industry-Academia Collaboration
INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUstry-Academia Collaborations
INNO	Innoget, member of the INDUSAC consortium
JSI	Jožef Stefan Institute, member of the INDUSAC consortium, project coordinator
KICs	Knowledge and Innovation Communities
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, member of the INDUSAC consortium
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PVI	Project Visual Identity
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SMEs	Small and Mid-Sized Enterprises
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
T	Task
WP	Work Package

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I. INTRODUCTION

The following report outlines the INDUSAC Communication Strategy, which details the comprehensive approach adopted by the project to encourage effective dissemination, exploitation, and communication of its outcomes. The Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for the Industry-Academia Collaborations (INDUSAC) project, funded under the HORIZON EUROPE initiative, endeavours to develop and validate an advanced Industry-Academia Collaboration (IAC) mechanism. This mechanism, centred around quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation, aims to enhance collaboration between industry and academia by addressing the needs and interests of stakeholders in the European Union, with a particular focus on widening and associated countries.

The INDUSAC project is highly digitalised and involves two main components: a methodology developed through human-centred design principles and an online platform that facilitates stakeholder connectivity and supports co-creation efforts. The project aims to refine its mechanism and deliver a tested framework ready for replication and upskilling by the end of the project by supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams. Additionally, the project endeavours to cultivate a dynamic community comprising at least 1000 companies, 3000 students, and 300 researchers.

The report also provides an overview of Work Package 4 (WP4) - Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication, which aims to amplify the impact of INDUSAC's results beyond the consortium. By employing various communication tools and strategies tailored to target groups, WP4 endeavours to ensure competitive positioning of project outcomes in alignment with current policies and European strategies.

Furthermore, the report outlines a timeline for communication and dissemination activities, emphasizes continuous evaluation of performance, and delineates the management structure for dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy. It highlights the pivotal role of partners in actively engaging with dissemination efforts and underscores the importance of internal communication to facilitate knowledge transfer and collaboration among consortium members.

The report also details the visual identity of the project, including the INDUSAC logo and associated branding elements. Additionally, it outlines various dissemination channels such as the project website, social media, audio-visual materials, and traditional press releases, along with their intended impacts and target audiences.

In summary, the INDUSAC Communication Strategy report underscores the project's commitment to fostering effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation of its outcomes, thereby maximizing its impact on industry-academia collaboration and contributing to broader societal and economic objectives.

II. INDUSAC COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

1. Overview

The Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUStry-Academia Collaborations (INDUSAC) project is a HORIZON EUROPE project that aims to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia Collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. The goal of INDUSAC is to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries.

Of a highly digitalised nature, the project INDUSAC will pilot the mechanism's two main components:

- methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles
- online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and supporting them throughout their co-creation journey

The INDUSAC methodology will provide the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform will stand as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions.

Figure 1 : Visual representation of the INDUSAC Concept

Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community

of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students and 300 researchers by project end.

INDUSAC is strengthened by a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial, and geographically balanced partnership that brings in the needed expertise and network to achieve the project goals.

2. Description of WP4

The main goal of WP4 - Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication is to broaden the impact of INDUSAC's results beyond the consortium itself by appropriate documentation, publication and promotion towards targeted stakeholders. All INDUSAC partners under the coordination of EIT will communicate and disseminate the project results to a wide range of target groups including the public, making use of a set of target-group adapted and tailor-made communication tools. At the same time, special attention and effort will be dedicated to the "internal" exploitation of the generated know-how, both from the new mechanism and the innovation projects that will validate it. WP4 will ensure that the results obtained are competitive at all times with other co-creation approaches and in accordance with current policy and European strategies on circularity, general sustainability, industry 4.0 and digitalisation. WP4 will also focus on aligning results to market developments so that the project outcomes are relevant beyond the project's completion. It will also contribute to the replication of project results to other sectors, cross-cutting themes and EU regions.

WP4 contributes to achieve Objective 6 and the exploitation, dissemination, and communication of the project.

2.1. List of deliverables of WP4

Table 1 : List of deliverables of WP4 Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication

Deliverable no.	Deliverable title	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due date (in months)
D4.1	INDUSAC communication strategy and materials	8 - BIC	Report	Public	3
D4.2	Project identity: brand, marketing basics and website	8 – BIC	Report	Public	6
D4.3	Periodic KPI updates related to communication and dissemination: performance monitoring	8 - BIC	Report	Public	12, 24, 36
D4.4	Exploitation plan: activities to be carried out to enhance the successful exploitation of the results	3 – BAX	Report	Sensitive	12
D4.5	Informative virtual event	8 – BIC	Other	Public	14
D4.6	Replication of the mechanism including business plan for the joint venture business	3 – BAX	Report	Sensitive	36
D4.7	Policy brief including policy recommendations	3 – BAX	Report	Public	36

2.2. Timeline

The activities of WP4 are closely linked with the other work packages. The overview of the communication and dissemination timeline is presented below (Figure 2).

Figure 2 : Gantt chart of WP4

2.3. Evaluation of the Performance

The dissemination and exploitation progress will be continuously monitored through the creation of a tool to collect and track the activities performed as well as the individual interactions made by the project partners. The plan will be updated, adapted and improved with additional activities as required.

The main communication activities are reported in the table below as well as the groups targeted and the related Key Performance Indicators (KPI) to measure the communication efforts and impacts:

A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) has been specifically defined to measure the communication and dissemination efforts and impacts: These indicators are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 : Summary of key performance indicators of WP4

Action	Description	Target audience	Performance Indicator
Project visual identity (PVI)	A logo, a PVI manual (logo, isotype, fonts, colour palette), and presentation and deliverables templates will be designed. The manual will be applied to all communication and dissemination activities.	Companies, researchers and students	PVI manual will be distributed Among partners before M3
Website	The website set up and managed by BIC will be the anchor for all communication and dissemination activities. The content will be adapted as the project progresses and maintained during the 3-year project duration and after the project to support exploitation.	Society in general	> 4,000 visits > 15,000 pages viewed > 2,000 users
Social Media	The project will open a Twitter and a YouTube account. Partners will post about INDUSAC on their corporate and personal Social Media accounts and participate actively in LinkedIn groups on the project's fields.	Students, companies and researchers	+100 Twitter followers +20 social media posts on Partner's account.
Media Relation	Press releases written and sent to traditional and specialised media outlets. Partners will adapt them to their corporate language and make them circulate throughout their own communication channels.	Cluster associations, KIT and EITs.	> 4 press releases (media) > 20 articles published outlets
Promotional Materials	A flyer and rollup will be designed to be distributed. The materials will be designed in M3 and updated on M32 to add information on the results achieved during the project. A general presentation of the project and poster layout will be produced in M6 (updated by M32) and will be used for events.	Companies, researchers and students	Proof of Materials designed in interim reports

3. Management of dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy

The coordination and oversight of the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities will be led by BIC, with the support of the lead beneficiary of WP4, EIT. All partners will contribute to the implementation of the communication and dissemination activities. BIC will be leading and coordinating the following communication and dissemination parts of the project: task 4.1 Communication and dissemination strategy and implementation.

BIC will be responsible for preparing all promotional materials and tools defined in D4.1. BIC as Communication Leader will also maintain the website, social media accounts, etc.

All INDUSAC partners consider that beyond promotion actions, active engagement is necessary to ensure enough participation of companies and other value chain stakeholders in the project, so they will support BIC in all dissemination activities to increase the engagement level of companies with INDUSAC. All partners will contribute evenly to WP4, delivering the required input for each task (in terms of region, communication with members, related networks etc.).

Academic and research partners will be responsible for disseminating the project results to the scientific community. Business-supporting organisations will be responsible for disseminating project advancements through their value chain members. BAX will coordinate all dissemination activities, identifying interesting opportunities for dissemination, and together with all partners represent the project in conferences, exhibitions, and other relevant events.

All partners are expected to be actively involved in the dissemination and communication actions' implementation to ensure that the project goals and satisfactory dissemination of the project's results are achieved. In general, the expected contributions from partners are to: exploit their contacts and networks to reach the identified target groups, promote the project in their own countries, and help to keep the project's social media accounts alive and active by contributing information and updates on the project in their countries or sectors, participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes and prepare their communication materials in accordance with project's visual guidelines.

4. Target audience

The promotion of results will be of great importance for INDUSAC. Below are defined the main target audiences, according to the objectives and most appropriate channels for reaching them:

- a) University students (undergraduates and master's students)
- b) Researchers (PhD students)
- c) Company staff (RDI staff or others) from SMEs and larger corporations
- d) Business clusters, university associations, chambers of commerce
- e) EIT KICs
- f) Policymakers at the regional and EU level
- g) SMEs and large corporations

All dissemination actions are planned to reach the targeted users and the wider spectrum of stakeholders most effectively and convincingly.

5. Internal communication

The internal communication strategy will focus on maximizing interaction and knowledge transfer between partners. INDUSAC will deploy a set of tools to maximize the effectiveness and efficiency of internal communication and collaboration, including:

- a) Online secure intranet featuring project and file management tools – dedicated project’s cloud, available only for the partners;
- b) Appropriate team mailing lists – contact list created by the Project Leader and uploaded to the project’s folder;
- c) Teleconferencing and video conferencing systems – ZOOM;
- d) Timetable of monthly meetings / Project calendar – uploaded on the project’s folder, includes dates of next meetings with the short agenda and information about participants;
- e) Timetable of project meetings / Project calendar – uploaded on the project’s folder, includes dates of next meetings with the short agenda and information about participants;

Templates – to facilitate the communication, document, deliverable and presentation templates will be created. They will be described in detail in D4.2. (M6).

6. Exploitation

Table 3 : Exploitation roles of partners

No	Partner	Role	Exploitation
1	JSI	RTD	JSI is interested in developing and implementing the mechanism that will enable researchers and students to generate the missing knowledge for the successful accomplishment of the company's R&D projects in 4-8 weeks as well as outside the scope of the project and after its completion.
2	KIT	RTD	Development of short-term co-creation approaches with the inclusion of human-centred aspects in development processes.
3	BAX	Innovation Consultancy	Build-up of knowledge in cross-cutting themes. Replication of the mechanism in a long-term financially sustainable way.
4	INNO	SME	Build-up of knowledge in online matchmaking processes and develop new modules that can be used as plug-and-play to existing open innovation platforms.
5	CIT	UNI	To exploit the collaborative mechanism, which might be interesting to both our clients (mainly SMEs) and our researchers/students.
6	CCI	Chamber of Commerce	To promote the activities of the project among the companies, universities, and research centres that are part of the 16 clusters connected to CCI and increase regional competitiveness.
7	CUT	UNI	To design, and develop research activities, focusing mainly on education, innovation, policy and demonstration.
8	BIC	Cluster association	To strengthen the cooperation between the scientific community and business. It is planned to promote the project and results among the 160 members - universities and companies.
9	EIT	EU body	New collaborations to build strong partner consortia to take part in future calls for proposals or other EIT initiatives. Interest in high TRL solutions.

7. Visual identity

As a first outcome, the INDUSAC visual identity was defined during the first two months of the project to make the project easily recognisable. The logo will be included in all communications to clearly identify the project. The visual identity will be used in all the materials produced under the frame of the project: presentation templates, project documents, flyers, roll-up, website, social media profiles, videos, etc.

Three preliminary versions of the INDUSAC logo have been designed by a professional design firm based on proposals from the partners of the consortium. The consortium has selected, by voting, the final version of the official logo of the partnership as shown below (Figure 3).

C:6 M:18 Y:94 K:0
R: 245 G: 204 B: 0
#f5cc00

C:90 M:78 Y:1 K:0
R: 57 G: 70 B: 150
#394696

C:12 M:9 Y:10 K:0
R: 229 G: 228 B: 228
#e5e4e4

C:53 M:42 Y:38 K:22
R: 120 G: 120 B: 125
#78787d

C:91 M:79 Y:62 K:97
R: 0 G: 0 B: 0
#000000

Figure 3 : The official INDUSAC logo with the colour palette

The official font used in the INDUSAC logo is Futura. For text, the official font of INDUSAC is Nunito Sans. Alternatively, the font CALIBRI can be used in communication within the consortium, e.g. in documents, emails, etc.

The main version of the logo is presented with the colour palette in Figure 3. The alternative (negative) versions of the logo are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 : Alternative versions of the INDUSAC logo

The INDUSAC logo has two key elements: the symbol and letters. The symbol forms a circle that resembles co-creation and collaboration. The circle is divided into three parts representing the capacity of participants: Academia, Companies and Digital Tools. The composition of the INDUSAC partnership directly responds to the need of having cross-sectorial experts from the academic and industrial world who are well connected to already existing industry-academia IAC mechanisms, together with experts in digital open

innovation. The letters include the project's acronym INDUSAC in bold typography. The typography is simple and direct. The colours for the project are black, grey, blue and yellow.

All dissemination activities, including promotional materials, will be adapted and in line with colour palette and fonts style of the logo. A detailed description of the project's logo will be presented in D4.2 Project identity: brand, marketing basis and website (M6).

8. Tools and channels

To disseminate the INDUSAC project objectives and outcomes towards the European community (including academia, industry and policy bodies, both at the national and EU level), different channels will be used, e.g. dedicated dissemination materials and communication actions produced at project level (e.g. press releases, INDUSAC presentations in conferences and other relevant events), and activities and channels of project partners (e.g. existing newsletters, specific events, etc.) will be leveraged. They are described below.

8.1. Online materials

8.1.1. Website

A dedicated project website will be prepared at the early stage of the project. Partners have chosen the domain by voting. The official domain will be www.indusac.eu

The objective of the website is to serve as a vehicle for the dissemination of the project activities and results. The main focus of the website is the external communication. The project website is also developed to facilitate information-sharing among the members of the consortium and between them and the public. The website will contain all relevant information about the project – description of INDUSAC and partners, news, events, open call opportunities, public deliverables, contact with the project partners, etc. The website will be updated on a regular basis (the content of the website will be described in detail in D4.2 (M6).

8.1.2. Social Media

Social media channels have become very popular means of disseminating information fast across various target groups. These channels serve on-demand access to content anytime, anywhere, on any digital device. To extend the project's target audience INDUSAC is integrating these media tools strategically in the communication activities. An INDUSAC account will be created on Twitter (Table 4) to disseminate information about the project, open calls, educational trainings, events and news from partners. Partners will post about INDUSAC on their corporate and personal social media accounts and participate actively in LinkedIn groups on the project's fields.

Social media channels will allow the project to share catchy messages for quick dissemination purposes and establish a virtual dialogue with the same channels of stakeholders, including relevant projects and initiatives.

Table 4 : Social media accounts of INDUSAC

Twitter		
	<p>Name of the profile: @INDUSAC_HE</p> <p>Official hashtag: #INDUSAC #HorizonEU #IAC #UCI</p>	<p>On Twitter, the project will publish relevant short news, calls, events, and partners activities related to the project. They will be aligned with information published on LinkedIn and the website.</p>

INDUSAC activities on social media seek the following impacts: making the project visible online, disseminating news about project deliverables, promoting open calls and events organised during the project, reaching target groups, ensuring effective real-time reporting of events, supporting the project networking.

The social media channels will be updated regularly by BIC as a leader of T4.1 on an ongoing basis throughout the duration of the project. English will be the main language used in social media. All the project partners will be engaged in social network dissemination activities and will collaborate to promote them in their communication channels. Especially one of our partner INNOGET (<https://business.innoget.com/#network>) as a global network of +180K innovators will disseminate the Innovation Needs as well.

8.1.3. Audio-visual materials

A YouTube account will be created where a series of knowledge capsule videos will be uploaded. The videos will present the key concepts of the project to the scientific and industry stakeholders. They will be shared on the INDUSAC website, social media and other dissemination channels.

At the end of the project (M36), one final promotional video with the project results will be produced by BIC and uploaded on the You-Tube account, websites and social media and officially presented in events.

8.2. Offline tools

8.2.1. Flyer, roll-up, project presentation, posters

A flyer and roll-up will be designed in M3. These materials will contain overall information as a brief description of INDUSAC, its objectives and opportunities for companies, researchers and students. The flyer will exist in electronic form to be forwarded via e-mail and downloaded from the website; furthermore, there will be printed versions to be used for conferences and physical events. The roll-up will be used also during all physical events, as well as a general presentation of the project and poster. Production of those

promotional materials will allow potentially interested stakeholders and the general public to be informed about INDUSAC.

8.2.2. Press releases and articles

Information about the project, open calls, its activities and results will be distributed in the form of press releases. Activities especially related to the identification and mobilization of relevant companies, researchers and students which constitute important phases of the project, will be widely highlighted via press releases. Press releases will be written and sent to traditional and specialized media outlets. Partners will be able to adapt them to their corporate language and make them circulate throughout their own communication channels. In general, every partner shall use the project's logo and its own logo if they deem necessary; if another partner's logo is to be used in any publications, this will be first cleared by the partner in question.

Journal articles are a broad-based dissemination tool. Due to the highly innovative character of the advances proposed in INDUSAC, it is of high interest to the consortium to disseminate the results obtained to both companies and research and students' community. For this aspect, a list of journals has been prepared in order to identify those which may be of interest for the results obtained and to reach a large audience.

8.2.3. Events

Various types of events will be organised during the implementation of the project. Matchmaking events will be an important tool to engage with the scientific and industrial community to provide them with an in-depth knowledge of the INDUSAC activities. Workshops are part of WP1 and WP4 and their organisation/execution will be supported by the online platform in WP2, with the objective of reaching the maximum audiences across sectors.

Target audience: Academic and industrial community, policymakers.

Performance indicators: Organisation of 2 workshops: pre-validation of the mechanism (T1.2) and promotion and training (T4.1). >50 attendees each (the aim is to have at least 50% of students/researchers attending).

Final Event: A final event will be organised by JSI at the end of the project to present all outputs and results. It will be open to a wider audience including public authorities, students, researchers, companies and European institutions (approx. 200 people).

Consortium partners will represent the project at international, regional or local events (congresses, seminars, conferences, workshops, and fairs) to promote the project objectives and results. Examples of conferences and events that INDUSAC partners plan to attend are included in Table 5.

Table 5 : List of events of interest preliminary identified by INDUSAC partners (not exhaustive)

Name	Type	Frequency	Involved partners
Mobile World Congress (Barcelona, Spring 2023)	Fair/Congress: meeting point	Yearly	CIT will have booths in for promoting methodology and open calls, supported by BAX and INNO. The focus will be to foster registering in the platform and the creation of a database for further engagement in project activities.
Foro Transfiere (Feb 2023-2024)	Conference	Yearly	JSI will host this event to promote knowledge exchange between academia and industry, to strengthen the cooperation and transfer of innovations from research labs into industrial exploitation.
Forum Przedsiębiorczości Akademickiej	Forum	Yearly	BIC can promote the project goals, methodology, open calls, etc. during the event.

9. Partner reporting dashboard

In order to monitor all the dissemination activities carried out by the INDUSAC partners, the T4.1 leader will create the partners' actions reporting dashboard, an Excel sheet available online in the project's folder. It will include dedicated tabs to report: press clippings, posts on social media, scientific publications, attendant of events, etc. The tool has two main purposes: to monitor all dissemination and communication activities going on within the project and to keep track of all events that partners are attending and they are promoting the project. Partners will be requested to update the dashboard by adding the activities they carry out. The Communication Manager will regularly check the dashboard and refresh the progress of the specific KPIs in order to make a close monitoring about dissemination efforts.

10. Obligations and requirements for communication actions

Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- a) display the EU emblem and
- b) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not however give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

YES:

NO!

Figure 5 : Correct (YES) and incorrect (NO) use of the EU emblem

A graphic guide to use the EU logo is available here:

<http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains:

“The content of this [insert appropriate description, e.g. report, publication, conference, infrastructure, equipment, insert type of result, etc.] represents the author’s view only and is his/her sole responsibility. The European Commission and the Agency do not accept any responsibility for use that may be made of the information it contains.”

III. INDUSAC MATERIALS

1. Templates

During the first three months of the INDUSAC project BIC as the T4.1 leader prepared some templates to use by the consortium in all communication and dissemination activities. They have been designed in line with the project's visual identity. Three templates were prepared:

- a) Document template (see Annex 1)
- b) Deliverable template (see Annex 2)
- c) Presentation template (see Annex 3)

All templates are available for all partners on a dedicated WP4 Communication and Dissemination folder in the project's cloud.

IV. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 : Document template

ANNEX 2 : Deliverable template

ANNEX 3 : Presentation template

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ANNEX 2: Deliverable Template

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DELIVERABLE

Version ...

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MM YYYY

Project Number: 101070297

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<i>Resubmission Date (based on EC feedback)</i>	
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<i>Reviewer(s):</i>	
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<i>Dissemination level:</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU <input type="checkbox"/> SEN

History of Changes:

Date	Comments	Version
	<i>eg. initial draft by partners responsible</i>	V0.1
	<i>eg. draft based on feedback from project partners</i>	V0.2
	<i>eg. draft based on feedback from Steering Committee</i>	V0.3
	<i>eg. final version submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V1.0

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students and 300 researchers by project end. The INDUSAC counts with a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that counts with the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

... Text

LIST OF ACRONYMS

EGZ xxx

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I. INTRODUCTION

Lorem Ipsum, lorem ipsum...

1. Lorem Ipsum

1.1. Xxx

Figure 1 : Title of figure / optional explanation

In the text, refer to Figures in a uniform way, for example (Figure 1) and not Fig. 1 or anything else.

Table 1 : Title of table / optional explanation

1.2. Xxx

1.3. Xxx

2. Lorem Ipsum

2.1. Xxx

2.2. Xxx

2.3. Xxx

3. Lorem Ipsum

3.1. Xxx

II. LOREM IPSUM ...

Lorem Ipsum, xxxxxx

1. Lorem Ipsum

- 1.1. Xxx
- 1.2. Xxx
- 1.3. Xxx

2. Lorem Ipsum

- 2.1. Xxx
- 2.2. Xxx
- 2.3. Xxx

3. Lorem Ipsum

- 3.1. Xxx
- 3.2. Xxx
- 3.3. Xxx

III. LIST OF REFERENCES

(includes referenced deliverables, datasets, articles, web pages)

- example of a cited deliverable: Surname, Name (for all authors) (Year): Deliverable title. Deliverable DX.X (Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (Horizon Europe project No. 101070297)) e.g. *Bastian, Annika; Rudolph, Paulin; Kempf, Christoph (2023): Predefined Collaborative Approach. Deliverable D1.2 (Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (Horizon Europe project No. 101070297))*
- example of a cited dataset: e.g. O'Donohue, W. (2017). Content analysis of undergraduate psychology textbooks (ICPSR 36966; Version V1) [Data set]. ICPSR. <https://doi.org/10.3886/ICPSR36966.v1>
- example of a cited article: Surname, Initials (for all authors) (Year). Title. Journal abbreviation, Volume, Issue, page numbers. <https://doi.org/xxx> e.g. *Rudolph P., Bastian, A., Kempf, C. (2023). User Journey Maps and User Guidance. Creativity and Innovation Management, 30(1), 83-95. <https://doi.org/10.2335/caim.1034>*
- example of a cited web page: URL + date of access e.g. <https://www.newcastle.edu.au/library/study-skills/referencing/apa7>, 10.05.2024

IV. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 : Xxx

ANNEX 2 : Xxx

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V. LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 : Xxx

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VI. LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 : Xxx

Table 2 : Xxx

Table 3 : Xxx

Table 4 : Xxx

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